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A Deployable Telescope Concept for Sub-Meter Resolutions

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Abstract. The use of synthetic aperture elements enables the development of telescopes with sub-meter resolution and considerably smaller launch volume, mass and thereby costs. As such, a space concept study yielded a competitive MicroSat Fizeau optical design with 25 cm ground resolution at 500 km orbital altitude. Its full-field Korsch design was optimized for compactness and wave-front quality. The primary mirror uses three aperture segments folded alongside the instrument during launch combined with a secondary mirror mounted on a deployable boom. A high image quality in space requires tight tolerance control of all mirror segment positions. Therefore, an alignment budget was derived using a sensitivity analysis.

Silicon Carbide mirror segments, Invar deployable arms and a main housing with active thermal control, enable operations with high thermal-mechanical stability. In orbit, the diffraction limited performance is controlled by a calibration system using interferometers and capacitive sensors to characterise the system. Actuators beneath the primary mirror segments correct their position to meet the required operational accuracy ranges. During operations, a passive system uses a phase diversity algorithm to retrieve the residual wave-front aberrations and de-convolve the image data

yielding the required end-to-end imaging performance. A rough first order bottom-up design using interferometers and capacitive sensors was made to comply with the top-down driven and required mirror rotation and alignment tolerance budgets down to 200 nrad and 100 nm. This indicated the potential compliance of top-down and bottom-up system engineering budgets to validate the healthy system design concept and to push it towards a robust design.

1 Introduction

High resolution Earth Observation (EO) data has become invaluable for a wide variety of applications, ranging from defence and security to environmental monitoring, precision farming and disaster response [25].

Presently, high resolution imaging data is captured by large, heavy and expensive EO systems such as GeoEye, Quickbird, Worldview and Spot [9, 4]. As a result, data produced by these satellite systems is also very expensive. Moreover, the number of systems capable of capturing imagery at a high resolution is still limited, while the swath width of these systems is typically small. This means that for many regions on Earth, frequently updated imagery is simply not available.

The goal of this work is therefore to design a deployable optical system that can reach similar resolutions as state-of-the-art EO systems, while using a fraction of

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TABLE 1. Design Specifications of the Deployable Telescope

Pupil Baseline	1.5 m
Focal Length	11 m
Swath Width	5 km
Field of View	0.57°
Aperture Area	0.65 m
GSD	Panchromatic (450-650 nm) 25 cm
	Blue (450-510 nm) 100 cm
	Green (520-580 nm) 100 cm
	Yellow (580-630 nm) 100 cm
	Red (630-700 nm) 100 cm

the volume and mass. The launch costs of such a system are therefore expected to be substantially smaller, which will ultimately result in a much lower cost per image. In Table 1, the main optical properties are listed that have been used as a starting point for the design. The ground resolution target and orbital altitude were derived from the Worldview-3 specifications [6], the recently launched 2800 kg EO satellite.

The paper is structured as follows. First of all, in Section 2, the systems engineering approach will be described that was used for designing a synthetic aperture system. Secondly, in Section 3 the optical design process is discussed. The section includes a trade-off between two synthetic aperture approaches. A conceptual mechanical design of the telescope is presented in Section 4 and in Section 5, its calibration aspects are discussed.

2 Systems Engineering Approach

Designing a synthetic aperture instrument for operation in a harsh and dynamic space environment is a complex task, particularly if the instrument needs to be unfolded in orbit. To ensure that the instrument can meet its required optical performance, independent lightpaths must be phased to a fraction of a wavelength. This difficult task is further complicated by the fact that the telescope will be operating in a Low Earth Orbit (LEO), where thermal loads are changing continuously. Active optical control and on-board metrology systems are therefore indispensable to accomplish such a task. Such systems must be used to measure and correct offsets in the position and orientation of critical optical elements.

Given the complexity of this design problem, coming up with a feasible design requires a sound systems engi-

neering approach. The approach which was used in this project can be characterized by the simultaneous application of bottoms-up and top-down system engineering principles.

From a top-down perspective, an optical design was created based on a set of top level requirements given in Table 1. Successively, an alignment budget is derived by performing a tolerance analysis. The budget takes into account potential image quality improvements that can be obtained using image processing algorithms, thus resulting in a somewhat more relaxed alignment budget, compared to a budget that would result from a tolerance analysis in which a diffraction limited performance must be achieved before any image processing comes into play. In a previous paper [8], the top down approach was already touched upon.

In the bottoms up approach achievable accuracies of the metrology and actuation systems are derived by performing a thorough analysis of these systems. In this analysis, limitations imposed by manufacturing effects, sensor noise, platform instabilities and temperature fluctuations are estimated and quantified.

Approaching the design problem from the top and bottom simultaneously, rather than sequentially, has several advantages. The main advantage is that the consequences of top level design choices on a subsystem level are already apparent in very early stage of the project. In a project phase where high level design choices are still somewhat flexible, this will allow for adjustments to be made to allow for a more feasible instrument design. A feasible design is obtained if the top-down alignment budget can be met with the achievable accuracies of the calibration system.

3 Optical Design and Trade-Off

When designing a synthetic aperture instrument, two main design architectures can be implemented [19].

In the **Michelson synthetic aperture**, a single large telescope is replaced by a number of afocal telescopes that are spread out across the pupil plane of the telescope. The telescopes produce collimated, magnified beams that are directed towards a beam combiner. The beam combiner focusses the light of each of the afocal telescopes onto a common image plane. A prominent Earth based example of a Michelson synthetic aperture are the Large Binocular Telescope [12]. A conceptual design of a Michelson synthetic aperture instrument will be described in Section 3.1.

The **Fizeau synthetic aperture** is similar to a conventional telescope. However, instead of a single monolithic primary mirror, a Fizeau synthetic aperture features a segmented primary mirror. The advantage of a segmented primary mirror is that these segments can be stowed in a compact volume during launch, to be spread across the baseline of the instrument after reaching orbit. An Earth based example of the Fizeau synthetic aperture is the Gran Telescopio Canarias (GTC) [13], while the planned James Webb Space Telescope is a prominent space-based telescope following the same design principles. In Section 3.2, a concept for a Fizeau synthetic aperture instrument is described in further detail.

A trade-off between the two approaches was performed, the results of which are described in section 2.

3.1 Michelson Synthetic Aperture

A fully reflective design for a Michelson synthetic aperture was created, which uses a set of 12 afocal telescopes that are distributed in an annular configuration across the pupil plane. Each of the afocal telescopes has an aperture diameter of 250 mm and an obscuration ratio of 0.4. The angular magnification of the telescopes is 5x, which was chosen to ensure that a compact beam combiner can be used. As a beam combiner, a full-field Korsch design was chosen, since it allows for a diffraction limited performance over a wide angular FOV. The use of glass components was deliberately avoided for two reasons. First of all, chromatic aberrations will complicate the image processing algorithms that are needed to obtain a good image quality. Secondly, the lower mounting stability of glass components when compared to mirror elements, would result in larger mechanical uncertainties.

Designing a Michelson Synthetic aperture for a wide Field of View (FOV) is a complex task, since raytrace applications such as Zemax do not natively support optimization through multiple parallel light paths [18]. The complexity lies in the fact that instrument must be modelled using non-sequential elements which, depending on the aperture configuration, can lead to a failure of many optimization operands. The beam combiner and afocal telescopes must therefore be designed separately, meaning that the interaction between the two components must be well understood.

The beam combiner, afocal telescopes and the system as a whole must meet a number of requirements to ensure that a diffraction limited performance can be

reached over a wide FOV [22]. First of all, both the afocal telescopes and the beam combiner have to be designed to produce a diffraction limited image quality over the full FOV. Secondly, the principle of homothetic mapping must be applied, i.e. the entrance pupil of the beam combiner should be an exact demagnification of the entrance pupil of the array of telescopes.

Finally, the afocal telescopes must be designed to produce a specified amount of distortion, known as sine-law distortion. As described in [27] this ensures that for off-axis fields, the wavefronts originating from each telescope remain in phase.

To ensure that the afocal telescopes have the appropriate amount of sine-law distortion, without sacrificing the wavefront quality, the afocal telescopes use aspheric mirrors. The shape of these mirrors can be described as a conic with 4 higher order terms. In Figure 1, a three dimensional view and a cross-section of the concept are shown. In the figure, the 12 afocal telescopes can be seen. They are spread in a circle with a diameter of 1.5 meter around the beam combiner. The beams originating from the afocal telescopes cross in the centre of the instrument before entering the beam combiner, which is needed because the afocal telescopes flip the image.

In Figure 2, the optical performance of the Michelson Synthetic Aperture is shown. The point spread function (PSF) is given for the most off-axis field, where the performance is worst. Both the polychromatic point spread function and the modulation transfer function (MTF) curves show that the system delivers a nearly diffraction limited performance for the full field of view. For the chosen aperture configuration, this leads to an MTF at the Nyquist frequency of approximately 10%. A slight degradation in MTF is observed when going to the outermost fields, at field angles of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. However, this drop remains limited to just 3% at low spatial frequencies (< 30 cycles/mm), while at higher frequencies almost no loss in resolving power is observed.

The full FOV that can be obtained with the Michelson system is limited to 0.2° , corresponding to a swath width of 1.75 kilometre. It falls short of the design goal of 5 km, given in table 1. A small extension in the FOV may be achieved with the current optical design. However, to reach the FOV goal, a substantial redesign of the afocal telescopes as well as the beam combiner is required. Steps that can be taken to achieve a wider field of view are reducing the angular magnification of the afocal telescopes, reducing the aperture diameter of these telescopes or using more, or more complex, optical elements. These steps will either lead to a substantially

FIGURE 1. *Optical Lay-out of the Michelson Synthetic Aperture*

FIGURE 2. *Polychromatic PSF and MTF of the Michelson Synthetic Aperture*

larger telescope, a reduction in aperture area or an increase the complexity. Therefore, it was decided not to undertake a redesign effort, since it would not change the outcome of the trade-off.

Compared to a conventional telescope, a reduction in launch volume of the telescope is mostly achieved by reducing the length of the telescope. Given the dimensions of the afocal telescopes, it is hard to design a mechanism which would allow them to be stowed in a more compact volume, since this would quickly lead to volume conflicts. Thus, it is not envisioned that using deployment mechanisms will lead to a more compact launch volume for a this instrument.

3.2 Fizeau Synthetic Aperture

Designing a Fizeau synthetic aperture system is a lot more straightforward than designing a Michelson system. The only difference between a Fizeau system and a conventional telescope, after all, is the shape of the entrance pupil. As a starting point for the concept, a full-field Korsch telescope [15, 16] was chosen for its compact size, good image performance and low distortions.

The primary mirror was split into rectangular segments, which can be folded towards the instrument body during launch. It was chosen to split the primary mirror into three segments, following an MTF analysis. Even though an increase in the number of segments leads to a slightly higher MTF at the Nyquist frequency

FIGURE 3. *Optical Lay-out of the Fizeau Synthetic Aperture*

FIGURE 4. *Polychromatic PSF and MTF of the Fizeau Synthetic Aperture*

of the detector, this increase is accompanied by a loss in contrast at lower spatial frequencies. Additional advantages of using three segments are the more compact stowed volume of the instrument as well as the increased simplicity of the deployment mechanisms.

The secondary mirror is placed on an extendible boom, further reducing the stowed size of the instrument. The design was optimized for a short distance of 1.1 meter between the primary mirror segments and the secondary mirror, to reduce mechanical uncertainties in the extendable arm. With this length, the obscuration of the telescope could be kept at 0.25. A further reduction in length led to a larger obscuration ratio, increased aberrations and results in stricter alignment tolerances on the secondary mirror.

In Fig. 3 the optical lay-out of the Fizeau system is

shown, while Fig. 4 on the next page shows the optical performance of the system.

As shown in Figure 4, the Fizeau synthetic aperture concept delivers a diffraction limited performance for the full field of view of 0.6° . In the MTF chart only one curve is visible, since the MTF curves overlap for the centre and the edges of the field ($\pm 0.3^\circ$) for the full frequency range. There is a considerable variation in MTF depending on the direction, which is a logical consequence of the pupil configuration. However, for all spatial frequencies up till the Nyquist frequency of the detector (90 cycles/mm), the Fizeau system has a higher MTF than the Michelson system.

TABLE 2. Trade-off between the Michelson and Fizeau systems. Scores between 0 and 5 were awarded for each trade-off criteria.

Criteria	Weight	Values		Scores	
		Michelson	Fizeau	Michelson	Fizeau
Stowed Volume	30	1.06 m ³	0.37 m ³	3	5
MTF	@ 50 mm-1	0.15	0.40	3	5
	@100 mm-1	0.08	0.17	2	4
Effective Aperture Area	20	0.36 m ²	0.57 m ²	2	3
Complexity	10	-	-	2.3	2.7
Field of View	8	0.2°	0.6°	2	5
Thermo-Mechanical Stability	8	-	-	2	3
Straylight Sensitivity	4	-	-	4	2
Weighted Average				2.5	4.0

3.3 Trade-off

A trade-off was performed between the two concepts. Below, a general description is given of the trade-off criteria and the relative performance of the concepts. The results of the trade-off are given in Table 2. A detailed description of the trade-off and the scoring systems that have been used are beyond the scope of this paper and is available for download at [7].

- **Stowed Size:** The stowed size was the most important criteria in this trade-off, as a compact launch volume greatly reduces the launch cost of the instrument and is a very important factor in bringing down the mass of the instrument. Therefore, it was given a high weight of 30%. The mass was not explicitly included in this trade-off, since it is strongly correlated with the instrument volume. In addition, large space structures are often constrained by volume rather than mass [21]. On top of that, it is very hard to get a reliable estimate at this stage of the project. With a stowed volume of 0.37 m³, calculated using CATIA, the Fizeau system is considerably more compact than the Michelson system, which has an estimated volume of 1.06 m³. Note that both systems are substantially more compact than a conventional telescope designed for the same ground resolution. Such a system is estimated to have a volume of at least 3.4 m³, computed by taking the bounded volume of the full-field Korsch design of the Fizeau system.
- **MTF:** The average MTF of both concepts was compared at the Nyquist frequency of the detector as well as half this frequency. As demonstrated in Fig. 3 and 4, at both spatial frequencies, the Fizeau system has a higher MTF and as such receives a higher score. MTF was given a high weight of

20%, since it is an important metric describing the image quality. It was not rated as highly as the launch volume, however, since some performance may be sacrificed if the cost of the instrument is brought down significantly.

- **Effective Aperture Area:** For this trade-off the effective aperture was defined as the product of the total aperture area and the system transmission. The parameter can be seen as driving for achieving a good Signal-to-Noise (SNR) ratio. The Michelson system has substantially more optical elements in its optical path, resulting in a lower transmission, as well as a slightly smaller aperture area. Therefore, it receives a lower score. Like MTF, the effective aperture area is given a high weight of 20%.
- **Complexity:** The complexity of the two systems was compared on the basis of the number of optical components, the complexity of the surface types, the dimension of the largest optical component and whether or not the system uses moving parts. All in all, the complexity of the Fizeau system was determined to be lower than that of the Michelson system, primarily due to a much smaller amount of total parts. The Michelson system features 77 optical components, while the Fizeau has only 7. Complexity is given a weight of 10%, since it can lead to high system cost, but may be tolerated if it results in a substantially better performance in the other criteria.
- **Field of View:** With a full field of view of 0.6°, the Fizeau system has a wider field of view than the Michelson system, which can only reach 0.2°. A further increase in field of view is possible for the Fizeau system, while large design changes are needed for the Michelson system. Should the

Michelson system be redesigned, it will likely increase in size and complexity. Thus, it is expected that this would not increase its overall score. The field of view is given a relatively low weight of 8%, since the primary goal of a high-resolution imager is not to obtain a complete ground coverage, but rather to observe specific regions of interest. Thus, for many applications, a small swath width may suffice.

- **Thermo-Mechanical Stability:** The thermo-mechanical stability of the Michelson is expected to be much more critical than that of the Fizeau system, primarily due to the long path lengths between the afocal telescopes and beam combiner as well as the large number of components. In addition, an active control system for the Michelson system will require the addition of several optical components, while for the Fizeau system direct actuation of the optical components is possible. The thermo-mechanical stability is given a weight of 8% in this trade-off. The main reason for choosing this weight was that the design philosophy used in this study is to develop a system that can function despite the inherent instabilities and uncertainties associated with such an instrument.
- **Straylight Sensitivity:** The Michelson system features multiple intermediate images, which can be used for the placement of a field stop and has small apertures that can be effectively baffled. While the Fizeau system also has a field stop, its aperture is much larger and therefore much more difficult to baffle. As such, the system is expected to be more sensitive to straylight. Straylight is given a low weight of 4%, because at this point, only a qualitative analysis has been performed, which is not detailed enough to be a major design driver. In the qualitative analysis, potential straylight issues and possible mitigation strategies are compared for both concepts. A more quantitative study of the straylight characteristics of a deployable telescope is subject to future research.

As shown in Table 2, the Fizeau was a clear winner of the trade-off and was therefore used as the basis for further development. In the detailed optical design phase, very few changes were made to the design, since a diffraction limited optical performance was already achieved. In Table 3, a summary is given of some key performance parameters that can be obtained for the

TABLE 3. Key performance parameters of the final optical design

Strehl Ratio		>0.99
MTF	@ 100 mm ⁻¹	0.10 (s) / 0.23 (t)
	@ 50 mm ⁻¹	0.33 (s) / 0.32 (t)
SNR	ER: 0.3, SZA: 60°	100
	ER: 0.5, SZA: 23.5°	150

final optical design. The SNR values have been calculated for two different Earth reflectances (ER) and sun zenith angles (SZA) under the assumption that a detector with 128 Time Delay and Integration (TDI) stages is used. At the time of writing, linescan detectors with up to 256 TDI-stages are available [5].

3.4 Sensitivity Analysis

While the nominal optical performance of the deployable aperture telescope is excellent, this is by no means a guarantee for a good performance in the harsh and dynamic space environment. The telescope will be operating in a low Earth orbit and will go in and out of eclipse every 100 minutes. As such, the instrument will be subjected to continuously changing heat loads, which can affect the position and shape of the optical components. To analyse the sensitivity of the design to such changes, a tolerance analysis has been performed. The main goal of this analysis was to create an alignment budget which must be met to ensure a good end-to-end image performance. It was determined using extensive simulations that such a performance can be met, on the condition that the peak-to-valley wavefront error stays below 7 waves. If this condition is met, the passive calibration system to be described in Section 5 of this paper can be used to retrieve the wavefront and correct the image.

In order to keep the wavefront error below the stated value, the elements must be positioned with the accuracies given in table 4. The directions of the axes used in this table are as follows: for the primary mirror segments, the X-axis is parallel to the long side of the segment, while the Y-axis is parallel to the short axis. The Z-axis for all optical elements is parallel to the optical axis of the telescope. The budget was established following a sensitivity analysis in which the effect of offsets in every degree of freedom were analysed.

As can be seen, particularly for the primary mirror segments, the tolerances are very tight. Especially the tolerances on the positioning in the Z-direction and the tilts around the X- and Y-axis will be very challenging;

FIGURE 5. Histogram of P-V wavefront error for 1000 Monte Carlo iterations

it is clear that these values cannot be reached with a fully passive system. Therefore, underneath the primary mirror, actuators must be placed to ensure that the tilt and piston error of the segments can be controlled.

TABLE 4. Required position and orientation tolerances of the primary mirror segments (M1), secondary mirror (M2) and tertiary mirror (M3)

Element	Position (μm)			Tilt (μrad)		
	X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z
M1	1	2	0.1	0.4	4.5	0.2
M2	4	4	2	17	17	50
M3	10	10	5	17	17	50

The tolerances on the secondary and tertiary mirror are less challenging to meet. Even though the tolerances on the secondary mirror are approaching the limits of a passive system, an active system is not foreseen here. Should it prove impossible to design a deployment mechanism that can meet the tolerances, the errors in its position can be effectively compensated by the actuation system controlling the primary mirror segments.

A Monte Carlo simulation was run to check the wavefront error that could be achieved with the stated budget. A total of 500 runs was performed. In the histogram of Figure 5, the results of the analysis are given for three field of view. It was found that in 90% of the cases, the P-V wavefront error remains smaller than 6.3 waves for the complete field of view.

4 Mechanical Design

Using CATIA®, a conceptual mechanical design has been created for the deployable aperture telescope. In Figure 6, two views on the instrument are shown. A compact and lightweight design has been created. In the stowed configuration, the design fills a hexagonal envelope with sides of 35 cm and a height of 1.1 meter. Currently, the nominal mass of the instrument is estimated to be 75 kg. This figure includes the weight of the deployment mechanisms, the optical components, the instrument housing structure and the calibration mechanisms. It does not include the deployable baffle structure and the weight of the electronics.

On the left side of Figure 6, the backside of the lightweighted primary mirror panels is shown. The mirror panels will be made using a Silicon Carbide (SiC) substrate. This material has been chosen on the basis of its low Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE), high thermal conductivity, high stiffness and excellent lightweighting possibilities. Areal densities as low as 7.1 kg/m^2 have already been demonstrated [26]. The low CTE of SiC makes the system quite tolerant to a thermal offset of one the segments; when relying on phase retrieval algorithms, a good performance can be achieved for a temperature range of up to $\pm 5^\circ$ with respect to the desired operating temperature. This alleviates the requirements on the thermal control subsystem to a great extent compared to when an aluminium mirror would be used. For this material, the allowable temperature range would be 10 times smaller.

The primary mirror segments have been mounted on arms via three whiffles. This set-up was chosen to reduce load concentration at the connection points on the

FIGURE 6. *Two views on the deployable aperture instrument*

mirror substrate, while also allowing for Between the whiffles and the arms, actuators can be placed to control the tilt and vertical position of the mirror segments. The arms can fold downwards in the stowed configuration. Doing so, leads to the most compact stowed configuration. The arms are supported by an extending rod for additional stability during the measurements.

Not shown in Figure 6 is the deployable baffle, which will be added to shield the instrument from straylight. During launch and integration of the satellite, the baffle will serve the additional purpose of shielding the sensitive reflective surface of the primary mirror segments from impacts. Currently, inflatable structures are being considered, but the design of this is a subject of future research.

The secondary mirror has been connected to the main housing via three deployable Invar arms. The arms feature a hinge in the centre to allow the mirror to be folded towards the main housing. This type of deployment mechanism is also found in the conceptual design of the International X-ray observatory (IXO) [1]. In the stowed configuration, the arms fit within the gap that is left when the primary are folded downwards. The arms have been positioned in such a way that they do not create any additional obscuration of the entrance pupil.

The main housing connects the primary and secondary mirror mechanisms to the other optical components. The temperature of the housing will be actively controlled using small heaters to ensure that the thermal gradients within the housing remain minimal. An active

system is preferred here, since deformations in the tertiary mirror are highly undesirable, since they will lead to field dependent aberrations. Such aberrations are difficult to correct and will therefore complicate the calibration procedure.

In Figure 7, the deployment sequence of the instrument is shown. The secondary mirror will deploy first, followed by the primary mirror segments. Since the speed of deployment is not critical, only a small force is needed to drive the deployment. As such, motors placed on the hinges of the mechanisms can be used to deploy the mirror segments.

5 Calibration Strategy

As shown in Section 3.4, the deployable aperture system is very sensitive to misalignments of its optical elements. As such, a well-defined calibration strategy is of vital importance to ensure that a good image performance can be reached. In the left panel Figure 8, a schematic overview is given of the proposed calibration strategy.

The calibration strategy can be split up into two phases. The first phase will occur directly after launch and may be repeated periodically to correct for long-term drifts. The main goal of this calibration phase is to ensure that the optical components are positioned with the accuracies defined in table 4, which will result in a peak-to-valley wavefront error of 7 waves. The remainder of the wavefront error will be retrieved during operations using phase diversity techniques.

FIGURE 7. *Deployment Sequence*

As an input to the calibration system, range measurements using capacitive sensors will be combined with interferometric measurements of a number of control points on the optical elements. In addition, measurements of stars can be used to estimate the wavefront errors of the telescope. To do so, wavefront retrieval algorithms, such as the Gerchberg-Saxton algorithm, can be used [10].

5.1 Metrology and Actuation Systems

The onboard metrology system of the deployable telescope is still in an early stage of development. A brief summary of the current design baseline will be provided in this section. Further details can be found in [24]. The currently proposed system will consist of two main components

First of all, capacitive edge sensors will be placed on the edges of the mirror segments, to measure offsets of the mirror segments relative to one another, and relative to the main structure. Such sensors are commonly applied in ground-based astronomical telescopes, such as the Thirty Meter Telescope that is currently under development [23]. In future iterations of the design, the shape of the mirror panels will be adjusted to create larger adjacent surface areas between two mirror segments, thereby allowing for more accurate measurements of the relative alignment of each of the mirror panels.

Secondly, an interferometric system will be used to measure the position of several reference points located on the surface of the primary mirror panels. These reflectors can be either corner cubes, or, as described in [14] retro-reflective gratings. Such gratings can be manufactured directly onto the mirror surface or can be attached later. By tuning the grating such that it has

a low diffractive efficiency, the impact of the gratings on the amount of straylight is negligible. By tuning the power of the laser, the measurements will have a sufficient SNR, despite the low grating efficiency.

A preliminary system model was developed to assess whether the accuracies of the metrology baseline are sufficient to meet the top down budget defined in Table 4. Using the model, a detailed bottom-up budget was defined, which includes a wide variety of error sources, such as sensor noise, misalignments of retro-reflectors and capacitive sensors, thermal fluctuations and laser instabilities. From the model, it follows that with realistic, achievable, alignment tolerances, thermal stabilities and sensor noise values, the budget given in Table 4 can be met with sufficient margin. This became clear by the results of a first order bottom-up measurement and actuator system design using interferometers and capacitive sensors. This showed compliance with the top-down driven and required mirror rotation and alignment tolerance budgets down to 200 nrad and 100 nm. Finally, this indicated the potential compliance of top-down and bottom-up system engineering budgets to validate a healthy system design concept and to push it towards a robust design.

After the metrology system has determined the position of the key optical components, actuators can be used to correct the position of the primary mirror segments. A more detailed analysis of the actuator system still has to be performed. Actuators designed for terrestrial astronomical telescopes can meet the requirements, both in terms of their stroke and accuracy [17]. However, more research is needed to determine whether or not this technology can be adapted for usage in space.

FIGURE 8. Calibration Strategy

5.2 Phase Diversity

During operations, a phase diversity will be used to recover the residual wavefront error and subsequently correct the image. In a phase diversity system, two detectors are used to capture the same image. The second detector is placed at a known defocus distance with respect to the first detector. Phase diversity is based on the principle that there is a known difference between the generalized pupil function at the first detector and the second detector. The generalized pupil function $H(x, y)$ is given by Equation 1 [11],

$$H_n(x, y) = P(x, y) \exp \left\{ j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (W(x, y) + W_{\text{defocus}}(x, y)) \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $P(x, y)$ is the binary pupil function, λ is wavelength and $W(x, y)$ is the unknown wavefront which will be estimated. $W_{\text{defocus}}(x, y)$ is the known defocus contribution to the wavefront; for the detector placed in the nominal focus, this term equals zero. To ensure a stable convergence in the presence of noise and a decrease in computing time, it is convenient to parameterize the wavefront by a set of aberration parameters α . For this application, the wavefront coming from each of the three segments is parameterized with a set of 17 Zernike terms. It has been shown that by maximizing the cost function L_m , given in Equation 2, an estimate

can be obtained for the wavefront parameters α [20].

$$L_m(\alpha) = - \sum_{\mathbf{u} \in \chi} \frac{|D_1(\mathbf{u})S_2(\mathbf{u}) - D_2(\mathbf{u})S_1(\mathbf{u})|^2}{|S_1(\mathbf{u})|^2 + |S_2(\mathbf{u})|^2} \quad (2)$$

D_1 and D_2 in Equation 2 are the Fourier transforms of the images obtained with the first and second detector, while S_1 and S_2 are the Fourier transforms of the estimates of the PSF at the first and second detector. The variable $\mathbf{u}$ is used for the spatial frequency. The summation is done over the set of spatial frequencies χ within the passband of the instrument.

Two implementations of phase diversity were considered, as illustrated in Figure 9. In the first approach, which is generally shown in literature, a beam splitter is placed close to the focal plane, reflecting half of the light to the second detector which is placed at a known defocus distance. In the second approach, the second detector is looking at a slightly different field than the primary detector.

A major advantage of the second approach is that the two detector do not need to share the light coming from the telescope, resulting in twice as much signal on the detector. One issue which could cause the phase retrieval to fail is that the unknown component of the wavefront is different at the two detector locations due to spatial variations. However, since both detectors will be placed very close to one another, this effect is expected to be very small, as was later confirmed by a Monte Carlo analysis.

To validate the principles of the phase diversity, an

FIGURE 9. Two implementations of a phase diversity system

end-to-end analysis was performed using a combination of Zemax and Matlab modules. Perturbations were added to the optical model based on the budget given in table 4, after which wavefronts for both detectors were retrieved. The wavefronts were used to simulate the two images. Representative image noise was added before using the images in the phase diversity algorithms.

In Figure 10 some results of this analysis are shown for two different scenes. The blurred pictures show the image quality, or the lack thereof, of a system with a peak-to-valley wavefront error of 6 waves. The recovered images have been obtained when deconvolving the blurry image using the retrieved wavefront.

The success of the phase diversity process is evaluated by calculating the Residual Strehl ratio, S_{res} . The Residual Strehl Ratio is calculated using the difference between the recovered wavefront and the actual, modelled wavefront error. It can be calculated using Equation 3

$$S_{res} = \frac{\max_{x,y} [p_{res}(x,y)]}{p_{diff}(0,0)} \quad (3)$$

where p_{res} is the PSF calculated with the residual wavefront error and p_{diff} is equal to the diffraction limited PSF. If a Residual Strehl ratio of 1 is reached, the wavefront has been recovered perfectly. For values above 0.8, the difference between the recovered wavefront and the actual wavefront is smaller than the diffraction limit. As

FIGURE 10. Results of the end-to-end simulation. Both images were obtained with field-separated phase diversity.

such, image restoration with the recovered wavefront will result in a nearly diffraction limited image. For values above 0.4, already a vast improvement in image quality can be observed, although some artefacts may be visible.

The analysis was repeated 120 times for different combinations of alignment errors, for both implementations of phase diversity. In Figure 11, a histogram is shown of the residual Strehl ratios obtained with the analysis. It was found that in 70% of the analysed cases the wavefront was retrieved successfully and most detail lost due to misalignments was recovered. Furthermore, the success rate of the algorithm was almost the same for the beam splitting implementation and the field separated implementation of phase diversity. It should be noted here that both simulations were performed using the same Signal-to-Noise ratio. Although field separated phase diversity can result in lower image noise, it may be preferable to bring down the number of TDI stages. For the 30% of the cases in which the algorithm failed to converge, no systemic effects were observed. It is expected that with future refinement of the algorithms, using several techniques described in literature [3, 2], the success rate can be increased significantly.

FIGURE 11. Histogram of the residual Strehl ratio obtained with 120 iterations. The beam-splitting implementation of phase diversity was modelled here.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

Sub-meter resolution imagery has become increasingly important for disaster response, defence and security applications. This paper presents a promising concept for a deployable aperture instrument, which can deliver such images whilst using a fraction of the mass and volume compared to conventional telescopes. End-to-end performance simulations of the instrument and its calibration system show promising results. A good image quality was obtained, within the limitations of a synthetic aperture solution, despite inherent instabilities occurring in a deployable system. Compared to a conventional telescope with an annular pupil, the contrast and SNR ratio will be lower, but this limitation in performance is compensated by a reduction in launch volume of a factor 4.

The actual bottom-up and top-down system engineering budgets comply and validate a healthy design concept. These budgets will be continuously refined in a stepwise systematic approach to keep the system engineering process in tight control.

Future work will consist of the further optimization of the performance of the telescope and the continuation of the mechanical design efforts. A detailed design of the mirror mounts, deployment mechanisms and actuators will be created. Key components of the system will be bread-boarded and a detailed analysis of the thermo-mechanical stability of the system will be performed.

Other topics that will be addressed in the near future are the further development of the metrology and

actuation subsystems to be used in the post-launch calibration phase and the refinement of the phase diversity algorithms. In addition, alternative calibration approaches will be investigated, such as the alignment of the telescope through optimization of a sharpness criterion. This strategy could allow for a more robust and simple calibration procedure in orbit. Part of the work will be done within the scope of a PhD research project that is funded by ESA NPI, TNO and the Delft University of Technology. A continuously refreshing team of MSc students will work on the development of the system together with experts from diverse parties.

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